

Lasker Award of this Year Was Announced

Lasker Award, which is sometimes referred to as "America's Nobels", was announced on September 6th. Three scientists were awarded for their outstanding contribution to human papilloma virus (HPV) vaccine and related discoveries in cell growth and metabolic regulation.

The US Lasker Foundation announced that this year's Lasker Award for Clinical Medicine Research Awards were awarded to John Schiller and Douglas Lowy from the National Cancer Institute on the grounds that their work enabled the development of human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccines, which prevent cervical cancer and other tumors.

The Foundation said that HPV could cause female cervical cancer and other malignant tumors. Lowy and Schiller have taken a bold while appropriate way to design the blueprints for several safe and effective vaccines that were expected to help reduce the incidence and mortality of cervical cancer.

This year's Lasker Award for Basic Medicine Research was awarded to Michael Hall from University of Basel on the grounds that he discovered the nutrient-activated TOR protein and its important role in cell growth and metabolism regulation. The destruction of TOR protein can lead to many diseases such as diabetes, cancer and other diseases associated with other series of age-related diseases.

In addition, this year's Lasker Award of Public Service Award was awarded to the Planned Parenthood Federation of America to reward its work in providing millions of women with the necessary health and reproductive health services in the past century.

The Lasker Award was created by Albert Lasker, father of modern advertising, in 1946 in recognition of scientists, medical researcher and public service personnel or institutions who have made great contributions in the field of medical research. Eighty Lasker laureates have received a Nobel Prize.

About Author

Creative Biolabs is specialized in providing custom biotechnology and pharmaceutical services that cover the full scope of biotechnology needs of early drug discovery and development, such as [itc services](#), [antibody engineering](#), [antibody production](#), etc.

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